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Table of Contents

Table of Contents	3
Executive summary	4
Report on Human Microbiome data	5
Introduction	5
Molecular profiling	5
Amplicon Based Sequencing	6
Metagenomics and Metatranscriptomics	6
Metaproteomics	7
Metabolomics	8
Considerations for microbiome research using NGS	9
Other Data types	10
Imaging	10
Phenotype	11

Executive summary

Microbial communities have been found inhabiting different environments, including oceans, soils, animals, and humans. Recent advancements in sequencing technologies coupled with the development of advanced bioinformatic software analysis tools have allowed the scientific community to investigate these microbial communities at an unprecedented resolution and scale. Microbial communities associated with the human body include eukaryotes, archaea, bacteria, and viruses, and are collectively referred to as the human microbiome. The human microbiome gained increasing interest in the research community as several studies linked it with health and disease conditions in humans.

This internal report presents common data types that are commonly generated and used when studying the human microbiome. This report does not aim to be a complete review of all available biological data types but instead gives an overview and insights about those data types that are commonly generated when studying the human microbiome. Human microbiome data types can be broadly classified as “Molecular profiling” such as those derived from molecular sequencing methods, and “Others” to represent all those biological data not generated through sequencing approaches. The former mainly includes metagenomics and metatranscriptomics, while the latter comprises biological data such as metabolomics and imaging results. In this report, we further review the applications of the various microbiome data types.

Report on Human Microbiome data

Introduction

The human gut contains predominantly bacteria and many diverse microorganisms such as Archaea, viruses, micro-eukaryotes, and fungi. The human microbiome encompasses the microbiome in various body sites, like the skin, mouth, urogenital and gastrointestinal tract. The gastrointestinal, or “gut” microbiome as it is frequently referred to, is the most widely studied human microbiome. The interest in the microbiome is to investigate its effect on health and disease. For example, the human microbiome has been characterized and studied in connection to various diseases like Type 2 Diabetes, Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD), and various cancers, to name a few. The investigation of the microbiome involves its characterization, both on a species level (the various genera/strains present in a given sample), and at a functional level (the genes, molecules, and phenotypes expressed). This report aims to delineate the different data types obtained from a given microbiome sample, and at what level these data types can characterize the microbiome.

The advancement in sequencing technologies coupled with advanced computational workflows have substantially increased our capability to decipher the taxonomic and functional compositions of the host-microbiome environment highlighting potential avenues of disease prevention, diagnosis and treatment. In this report, we will review the existing microbiome data types and their applications in the current microbiome research (Figure 1).

Molecular profiling

Previously, studying human microbiome samples heavily relied on time- and labour-intensive techniques of growing and isolating individual organisms which were further followed by phenotypic or genotypic analysis. Microbial community profiling within a single sample was not possible with these older methods.

Molecular profiling comprises various methods to profile the biological content of interest in a sample. This can either be the identification of species and genomes (either through amplicon-based sequencing methods, or more comprehensive metagenomics), functional profiling, which mainly includes gene expression (metatranscriptomics), protein expression (metaproteomics), as well as metabolites (metabolomics). These are also the data types one expects in a truly “integrated” analysis of the microbiome. As these data types are also known as “omes”, any analyses involving results drawn from multiple “omic” data are referred to as “multi-omic” analyses.

Amplicon Based Sequencing

Amplicon Based Sequencing usually involves the characterization of the species present in a given microbiome sample, by detecting specific regions of the genome. These specific loci are chosen such that they are variable enough to distinguish between species, but are flanked by conserved regions that can be used for amplification by Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR).

Among bacterial communities, the most common loci are segments of the 16S rRNA gene. This codes for a component of the small ribosomal subunit, and is thus widely conserved and present in all organisms. It also contains 9 hypervariable regions that allow for distinction between bacterial genera and species. There are also multiple databases mapping specific 16S sequences to their respective organisms, making this one of the most widely used method for characterising microbial communities.

There are, however, certain drawbacks. There is a chance for false positives at the amplification stage as the primers could bind to regions that are not fully conserved. It is also not quite possible to differentiate between certain closely related species using this method.

Like the 16S rRNA subunit in prokaryotes, the 18S rRNA is an essential component of the eukaryotic small ribosomal subunit, and is used for the characterisation of eukaryotic organism/genomic content in a particular sample of interest

Internal Transcribed Spacers (ITS) are transcribed but non-functional regions of both prokaryotic and eukaryotic rRNA operons. There are multiple of these, one ITS in bacteria and archaea is located between the 16S and 23S rRNA genes, and there are two ITSs in eukaryotes - ITS1 and ITS2, which flank the 5.8S rRNA gene. ITS1 is the homologue of ITS in bacteria and archaea. The ITS region is the proposed barcode for fungal entities, as it has species resolution for a very broad range of fungi compared to other fungal marker genes.

Metagenomics and Metatranscriptomics

In recent years, shotgun metagenomics has gained significant attention, as it can sequence and obtain all genomic DNA, irrespective of its source, from a particular sample. This enables a much higher degree of characterization, usually at the strain level, and does not suffer the amplification biases associated with amplicon-based methods. While the costs associated with shotgun methods have been reduced, they still remain more expensive than

amplicon-based approaches. The key advantage remains that it is possible to obtain information on the entire genome of all dominant entities of a sample, including non-microbial ones, through shotgun metagenomics. This tells of relative abundances of taxa as well as their functional potential. This has proven invaluable in the study of the human microbiome, both in terms of characterization, and studying complex diseases.

Metatranscriptomic takes this a step further, enabling us to sequence all of the RNA in a particular sample. This gives us information on global-scale gene expression in the samples, and also arms us with the data needed to functionally profile communities in a given environment/disease state. This also helps identify actively expressed genes in metabolic pathways, and can be integrated with both metagenomics and metaproteomics/metabolomics to truly understand the mechanisms at play in a given site (eg. the gut, skin, saliva), or a particular disease. However, due to the relatively short half-life of RNA, metatranscriptomic methods may not accurately capture the actual gene expression landscape. Other limiting factors are the lack of sufficient material for sequencing, and the removal of rRNA prior to mRNA characterisation, as ribosomal RNA constitutes the vast majority of total RNA, and is not of particular interest while studying gene expression. Finally, as transit time in the colon is commonly around 20 hours in humans activity of the microbiota is not the of a very active microbial community and what it really tells of the ecosystem may be debatable.

These genomic and transcriptomic can be characterised by either short-reads or long-reads. Short read sequencing involves the simultaneous sequencing of short reads, usually <700bp. The steps one follows here are DNA/RNA extraction, barcoding, pooling, and sequencing. The sequencing here usually follows a sequencing-by-synthesis approach, and detects individual bases through either ion currents or base-specific fluors. In comparison, long-read sequencing characterises reads in the 10kbp range, and follows single molecule sequencing methods, with similar base detection strategies, either through fluorescence or ion currents. The lack of an amplification step here reduces biases in comparison with short read sequencing, and gives better overall resolution of genomes, facilitating better identification of genomic structural variants, and also helpful in assembly of large and complex genomes.

Metaproteomics

In contrast to metagenomics, metaproteomics is an emerging yet potent method, focussing on functionally characterizing the dynamic composition of microbial proteins in both health and disease.

Metaproteomics encompasses various strategies for identifying and characterizing the proteome (the complete set of proteins) within a microbial sample. In its early stages, metaproteomics involved the separation and

characterization of proteins using Electrophoresis (2D PAGE). However, with the advent of Mass Spectrometry (MS), MS-based approaches have become the predominant tool for characterizing the Metaproteome.

Metaproteomic analyses involve the following key steps: (i) extraction and purification of proteins, (ii) enzymatic digestion of proteins into peptides, (iii) separation of peptides using techniques like chromatography, and (iv) mass spectrometric analysis of the peptides, culminating in (v) the identification of peptides through databases.

In comparison to metagenomics, the field of metaproteomics for functionally characterizing microbial communities has a considerable distance to cover. Nevertheless, it seems to function as a complementary approach to metagenomics, serving as a tool for the comprehensive characterization of taxonomic proteins in microbial ecosystems. Future advancements in this field hold significant promise.

Metabolomics

Metabolomics is an emerging technology that is applied as a research discovery tool with the objective of non-targeted approaches to detect, and report normalised relative peak areas for as many metabolites as can be reliably measured. Univariate and multivariate analysis of the acquired data is subsequently applied to define the biologically important metabolites and generate hypothesis for further biological testing. The number of metabolites for which data are reported is dependent on the metabolome of the sample type, the sample extraction method employed as well as the analytical platform applied. Mass spectrometry (MS) is often used for performing metabolomic analysis, especially because of its good sensitivity and its capacity to detect and quantify a large diversity of molecules in complex biological samples. Although there is a challenge to perform analysis of metabolome data, there has been a vast increase in the recent years for development of tools to analyse MS-based metabolomics data, including improvements in feature extraction, annotation and data analysis to improve biological contextualization, including the integration with other omics data.

Semi-targeted (hybrid) studies are also a discovery tool but a target list of metabolites that are expected to be measured are predefined. The applied assay(s) allows collection of data to confirm the presence of each metabolite on the target list (cf. untargeted assays where data are collected to identify the metabolite structure).

Metabolomics is applied across the biological sciences from the study of microbial systems and their interaction with other biological systems (e.g. human gut microbiome), the study of the environment and its biological species to the study of mammals with a perhaps unsurprising large focus on humans. Metabolomics approaches are normally applied to answer one of two different types of question; either to identify prognostic or diagnostic biomarkers of health or disease or to identify new biochemical processes/pathophysiological mechanisms.

There is also an ever-increasing emphasis in the microbiome field on mechanistic understanding of how chemical environments shape microbial communities and a deeper interest in the effect of the microbially derived molecules on ecosystems. In comparison to sequencing which provides insights into the microorganisms that are present and the metabolic capacity, metabolomics is a direct readout of the function of a system. The metabolome is considered the closest representative of phenotypes and, therefore, metabolomics can provide insights into the cellular processes in response to some stimuli or interactions.

Metabolomics allows the profiling of the biological samples (such as biofluids, cells and tissues) - derived from humans, animals and the environment that exert multitude of functions with huge impact on human health and disease. For instance, high red meat and animal fat intakes have been well established as risk factors for both cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) and colorectal cancer. Genome-wide studies have established strong correlation between colorectal cancer and trimethylamine N-oxide (TMAO), a gut microbial metabolite of dietary meat and fat. TMAO is a gut-dependent metabolite that is generated from dietary choline and L-carnitine obtained from foods (red meat, egg yolk etc), which are first metabolised into trimethylamine (TMA) through gut microbiota metabolism and further converted to TMAO by hepatic flavin monooxygenases (FMOs). An elevated circulating level of TMAO has been identified as a risk biomarker in colorectal cancer.

The major methodologies employed to profile the metabolite compositions of microbiome-related samples include liquid chromatography–mass spectrometry (LC-MS) and nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy (NMR), which help in routinely measuring tens to hundreds of metabolites.

As with any emerging technology, the field of metabolomics also has its limitations, which include: (i) cost inefficiency, (ii) logistical challenges associated with large scale analysis, and (iii) inability to identify metabolites without existing standards.

Considerations for microbiome research using NGS

There are several factors to consider for a successful microbiome study. For NGS studies in particular, sequencing coverage and sequencing throughput are important concepts to ensure proper data is obtained to address scientific questions and objectives. Having appropriate coverage and sequencing throughput ensure that there is sufficient data to genetically characterise the microbiome. This includes determining the number of OTUs from the samples.

Long NGS sequencing reads can help address coverage considerations by enabling researchers to sequence difficult regions of the genome. Longer sequencing reads are also more unique and can be more accurately assigned to an appropriate reference genome, or be grouped for an unknown species that is not within the genomic database. Thus, a more accurate classification of microbes in the microbiome can be achieved. Sequencing accuracy is an important consideration to ensure the correct sequencing variants are being called. Poor accuracy can lead to an inflation in defined OTUs and thus an overestimate in microbiome diversity.

Given the microbiome is a complex ecosystem, one can see how the data would be difficult to analyse with sequence information from thousands of microbial species and strains. This can be further compounded by sequencing numerous samples taken from different sites on a single individual, across a human population, and even over a temporal scale. The bioinformatics analysis and computation requirements need to be considered during study design.

Other Data types

Imaging

Histopathology has been invaluable in our study and understanding of various diseases, be it from either looking at blood samples on a glass slide, or advanced biopsies of tumours. Recent advances in imaging technology, such as immunofluorescence to detect particular metabolites/peptides, or Fluorescent in-situ Hybridization (FISH), to detect expression of targeted genes, have also started becoming important in the field, and cannot be ignored. There have been studies that have established that elimination of microbiota accessible carbohydrates (MACs) from the diet results in thinner mucus in the distal colon, resulting in increased proximity of microbes with the epithelium, and heightened expression of inflammatory markers REG3 β in cancer patients. FISH can also be used against 16S rRNA markers, to label specific bacteria in host tissues, to understand their spatial organisation.

Defining the composition and spatial heterogeneity of the microbiome is critical to facilitate further understanding of the gut microbiome ecology. Many studies have highlighted that bacterial communities in the gut are spatially distributed and any disruption to that spatial structure of the gut might often lead to a common underlying feature of disease pathogenesis. In the last few years, there has been increased interest leading from analyzing gut diversity through sequencing an entire microbiome community towards understanding the spatial distribution and organisation of a gut microbiome.

In this direction, Metagenomic Plot Sampling by Sequencing (MaPS-seq), is a culture-independent method developed to characterize the spatial organization of a microbiome by analyzing the sequences of microbial cells in

their natural environment. Intact microbiota samples are fractured into particles and are encapsulated in droplets before deep sequencing. This results in the retention of spatial information and can identify species that tend to co-localize in complex samples such as the gut microbiota. With this method, it's possible to statistically reconstruct the local spatial organization of microbiomes.

Culturomics and isolates' phenotype characterization

Large scale metagenomic assembly unveiled a vast majority of species that are not similar and not represented or mapped to any available reference genomes. High throughput culturomics aim to isolate and characterize these unknown species. Their characterization and formal identification relies on wet-lab assays to characterize their phenotypes. These could, for example, use gram staining, analysis of optimal pH conditions, ideal growth temperature, and preferred growth substrates (High Fibre for example), and anaerobic or facultatively anaerobic growth conditions.